

SELF-ASSEMBLED “BRICK-AND-MORTAR” NANOSTRUCTURE INSPIRED BY NATURE: A ROUTE TOWARDS HIGH MECHANICAL PERFORMANCE NANOCOMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A hybrid nanostructure was assembled via Layer-by-Layer (LBL) assembly to produce a “brick-and-mortar” (LDH/PSS)_n coating similar to natural nacre, but with all dimensions scaled down consistently by more than one order of magnitude. Quality of the films was confirmed by optical absorption, microscopy and X-ray diffraction rocking curves. A high loading of LDH platelets, about 88.4 wt%, embedded in PSS, formed a “brick-and-mortar” nanostructure with distinct layer arrangement leading to an elastic modulus and hardness of $E = 65.8$ GPa and $H = 2.34$ GPa, respectively. Substantial plastic deformation, strain hardening caused by platelet sliding and interlocking and the ability to deflect a propagating crack were evidenced. The classic behaviour of natural nacre appears to be well replicated at shorter length scales, as long as the organic content is kept low and the inorganic platelets organised in a “brick-and-mortar” structure. By scaling down the dimensions of natural nacre, a larger amount of plasticity was observed in the material upon mechanical loading compared to natural nacre as a result of larger absolute platelet interface density.

1 INTRODUCTION

Natural composites, especially the hybrid nacre structure found in the inner part of molluscs shells, have inspired researchers to design new lightweight composite materials with exceptional mechanical properties. Nacre is one of the strongest composites found in nature and part of a two-layer shield system used by seashells as protection from their environment ^[1]. Its structure is composed of 95 % of brittle, inorganic aragonite (CaCO₃) building blocks around 200 to 900 nm thick and 5 to 8 μm wide ^[2]. These CaCO₃ building blocks all have same crystallographic orientation, parallel to one another, as a result of a mineralisation process. The blocks are organised in a “brick-and-mortar” structure, “glued” together by a ductile and soft biopolymer. This organic layer is around 20-30 nm thick ^[3, 4], which makes up the remaining 5 % of the structure ^[5-7]. This combination of a small fraction of organic phase along with this specific architecture and tight three-dimensional arrangement leads to

exceptional mechanical properties, including high toughness ($\approx 1.24 \text{ kJ.m}^{-2}$), strength ($\approx 140 \text{ MPa}$) and stiffness ($E \approx 60 \text{ GPa}$)^[8, 9], especially given the poor properties of the constituents. Its toughness is three orders of magnitude higher than that of the aragonite tablets alone^[10]. Upon mechanical loading, the building blocks have the ability to slide over one another within the organic phase and eventually interlock^[11, 12] providing strain hardening^[4, 13] and good strength. In addition, the highly aligned and anisotropic inorganic “bricks” compensate for the 5 % of low elastic modulus matrix^[14], resulting in a high stiffness hybrid. When a crack initiates from a defect within the nacre structure, it is deflected at the building block interfaces^[15]; the platelets themselves slide and interlock in the vicinity of the crack tip, via a range of possible mechanisms^[3, 4, 16], leading to strain hardening and crack deflection. These effects increasingly spread the deformation, leading to substantial energy dissipation and hence defect tolerance^[17, 18]. The mimic of the “brick-and-mortar” structure of natural nacre at a smaller length scale while retaining the specific geometry and proportions of each phase should allow the reproduction of the classic deformation mechanism, mechanical properties with an increase in energy absorption *via* the activation of a greater volume of platelet interface per unit volume^[19, 20].

Here, the use of well-defined $\text{Mg}_2\text{-Al-CO}_3\text{-LDH}$ platelets as inorganic reinforcement has been explored, with a width of 50 and 130 nm. The aspect ratio of these platelets approaches that of aragonite plates in natural nacre^[2]. The thickness of the platelets means that the soft polymer layer can be thinner than the platelets, resulting potentially in nacre-like structures with the correct phase volume fractions. Reduction of the organic matrix content to levels close to that of natural nacre impacts the morphology, alignment and mechanical properties of artificial nacre-like coatings. LDH platelets were selected for their dimensions, charge density (brucite-like cationic surface) and composition that can be easily adjusted using a co-precipitation method followed by a hydrothermal treatment^[21]. LDH platelets with highly charged surfaces were synthesised and dispersed in water so that a stable dispersion was achieved. A Layer-by-Layer (LBL) assembly method was selected to enable the deposition of monolayers of organic and inorganic materials^[22, 23], allowing the alignment of anisotropic nanoplatelets through electrostatic attraction during adsorption. Indeed, electrostatic attraction of oppositely-charged particles, such as LDH platelets and organic polyelectrolyte polymer chains, can produce a well-organised nanostructured coating by sequential dipping. Here, negatively-charged LDH platelets were combined with PSS polyanions.

2 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

$\text{Mg}_2\text{-Al-CO}_3\text{-LDH}$ platelets with a mean width of 49 and 131 nm were synthesised *via* a coprecipitation method followed by hydrothermal treatment at 100°C for 4h (LDH-1) and 72h (LDH-2), respectively, and diluted further in water without aggregation. Dispersions in water formed stable electrostatically-stabilised colloids with re-aggregation starting only after a couple of months during storage at room temperature. LDH platelets in water had a ζ -potential at pH 10 (in 5mM KCl) higher than +30 mV. According to the TEM images and XRD characterisation (Fig.1), the platelets exhibit anisotropy with a mean aspect ratio ranging from 6 to 10. Only XRD reflections corresponding to pure hydrocalcite were observed, confirming the formation of a phase-pure. Sharper (003) diffraction peaks, related to the crystallographic plane parallel to the surface of the platelets, were measured for LDH-2 platelets, indicating a higher thickness about 13.6 nm compared to 8.6 nm for the LDH-1 platelet.

Figure 1. $Mg_2-Al-CO_3$ -LDH platelet structure and dimensions. XRD diffractograms of LDH-1 and LDH-2 platelets (A and B). TEM width analysis and images of LDH platelets (C and D, respectively)

The use of an anionic, PSS polyelectrolyte, allowed for alternative assembly of a $(LDH/PSS)_n$ multilayer coating on glass slides. Indeed, the dipping of a charged glass substrate such as glass or quartz slide into oppositely charged particles allowed for the deposition of monolayers via Layer-by-Layer assembly through electrostatic attraction forces while the excess of material loosely attached to the substrate was washed off during subsequent water rinsing steps. The deposition of a first monolayer of LDH onto a glass slide was investigated by SEM and AFM, revealing a homogenous monolayer with neither platelet overlapping nor particle excess (Fig.2).

Figure 2. LDH and PSS monolayer deposition on glass slide. SEM images of LDH-coated glass slide with loosely attached particle excess, LDH monolayer-coated and LDH/PSS bilayer-coated glass slide (A, B and C, respectively). AFM height profile of LDH monolayer deposited on glass slide (D).

The progress in layer deposition on the quartz slides was monitored by UV-Vis spectroscopy (Fig. 3.C-D). The absorbance band at 225 nm is related to the phenyl group of PSS^[24], while the scattering within the whole range of wavelength is attributed to the platelets. Linear increase in absorption of both PSS and LDH-related features with increasing number of bilayer deposition, confirmed monolayer deposition of the two layers, PSS and LDH, with repeatable thickness. A homogeneous deposition of the multilayer coating on quartz was achieved, as evidenced by visible reflection from the coated slide (Fig.3.A).

Figure 3. $(\text{LDH/PSS})_n$ multilayer deposition on quartz slide. Schematic of Layer-by-Layer assembly of alternate LDH and PSS layers on a glass/quartz slide (A) and pictures of coated quartz slides (~ 0.5 and $1 \mu\text{m}$ -thick coating, 1 and 2, respectively). XRD diffractograms of pure LDH powder and $(\text{LDH/PSS})_n$ coating (B). UV-Vis spectra of $(\text{LDH/PSS})_n$ coating deposited on quartz (C) and the related absorbance at 225 nm as a function of the number of deposited (LDH/PSS) bilayers n (D)

Both XRD diffractograms (Fig.3.B) and thermal gravimetric analysis of the $(\text{LDH/PSS})_n$ coatings indicate the presence of polymer. An increase in the inorganic content from 57.3 wt% to 88.4 wt% was measured when the LDH platelet dimensions were increased from $49 \pm 16 \text{ nm}$ (LDH-1) to $131 \pm 44 \text{ nm}$ (LDH-2), respectively. This inorganic content is approaching that of natural nacre (95.7 wt%)^[25].

SEM images show a good orientation of the LDH platelets present in the top layer of μm -thick coatings deposited on glass slides (Fig.4.A); the platelets were still parallel to the substrate after the deposition of multiple bilayers. Three-dimensional XRD rocking curves were acquired at a fixed 2θ angle of 11.7° (corresponding to the (003) interlayer reflexion normal to the LDH platelets) to study the alignment of the platelets to the substrate. The misalignment values were obtained from the Full Width at Half Maximum (FWHM) of the rocking curve. The $(\text{LDH-1/PSS})_n$ coating presents a misalignment of $\pm 20^\circ$ compared to only $(\pm 8^\circ)$ for the $(\text{LDH-2/PSS})_n$ coating.

Mechanical properties of the two nanostructures deposited on quartz substrates were determined by nanoindentation using the Oliver and Pharr method^[26]. The load-displacement curves and related mechanical properties (Tab.1) obtained for the different coatings were then compared to each other, as well as to natural nacre which has an elastic modulus and hardness of about $E = 40\text{-}70 \text{ GPa}$ and $H = 3\text{-}4 \text{ GPa}$ ^[4, 27, 28], respectively. Elastic moduli of 27.7 and 65.8 GPa were measured for

(LDH-1/PSS)_n and (LDH-2/PSS)_n coatings, respectively. The elastic modulus of (LDH-2/PSS)_n represents the highest value measured for an artificial nacre via nanoindentation, highlighting the importance of producing nanocomposites with high and organised inorganic fraction. Regarding the hardness of the coatings, an increase from 1.35 to 2.34 GPa was measured for coatings containing LDH-1 and LDH-2 platelets, respectively. All coatings tend to creep intensively during the first 10 s of the holding segment and then progressively stabilise, confirming a viscoelastic response of the organic phase.

Different shapes of the load-displacement curves were also observed. Well-arranged (LDH-2/PSS)_n coatings progressively harden. (LDH-1/PSS)_n coatings show constant resistance to mechanical load with less rigidity. The strain hardening observed for (LDH-2/PSS)_n coating with well-arranged LDH monolayers can be related to an in-plane sliding of the platelets and subsequent progressive platelet interlocking. This strain hardening phenomenon of (LDH-2/PSS)_n coating is similar to that of natural nacre^[3], which requires a small amount of organic phase and a good “brick-and-mortar” three-dimensional organisation of the platelets for its specific mechanisms to operate. The amount of yielding during indentation of the (LDH-2/PSS)_n nanostructure was measured to be higher than that of the (LDH-1/PSS). A 3.5 µm-thick (LDH-2/PSS)_n coating was also deposited on a glass slide in order to investigate the degree of yielding in the materials while indenting it with a sharp cube-corner tip at varying depth (Fig.4.B). A stabilised degree of yielding^[29] of about 95 % was measured, which is higher than that of natural nacre (78%).

Figure 4. Mechanical properties and deformation of (LDH-2/PSS)_n. SEM image of 1.5 µm-thick (LDH/PSS)_n top surface after deposition (A). Nanoindentation of 3.5 µm-thick (LDH/PSS)_n at various load with a cube-corner tip (B). SEM images of high-load- indented 1.5 µm-thick (LDH/PSS)_n (C and D)

Nanoindentations at high load (~150 mN) were also carried out in order to investigate the deformation mechanism of the nanostructure in the vicinity of the indent. Low inorganic loading nanostructure containing LDH-1 platelets was observed to form homogenous and smooth pile-ups as a result of platelet flowing in the organic phase. On the other hand, the high inorganic loading (LDH-2/PSS)_n nanostructures exhibit progressive propagations of materials that sequentially arrest (Fig. 4.C). This feature is a signature of an in-plane platelet sliding followed by progressive friction and eventual interlocking, leading to strain hardening. Crack deflections were also observed when a crack was initiated from the edge of the indent upon high loading (Fig.4.D), similarly to natural nacre.

LDH Platelet	LDH platelet dimension			(LDH/PSS) _n nanostructure		(LDH/PSS) _n mechanical properties		
	Thickness / nm	Width / nm	Aspect ratio	LDH content / wt.%	LDH align. / %	E / GPa	H / GPa	Yielding / %
LDH-1	~8.6	49 ± 16	~6	57.3	78	27.68 ± 0.98	1.35 ± 0.06	~ 70
LDH-2	~13.6	131 ± 44	~10	88.4	91	65.79 ± 3.16	2.34 ± 0.18	~ 95

Table 1. Properties of (LDH/PSS)_n nanostructures

3 CONCLUSIONS

The “brick-and-mortar” structure of nacre was mimicked at a nanometre length scale with good platelet alignment and high platelet volume fractions when using suitable platelet dimensions. The artificial nacre nanostructure developed represents significant advancement in the mimicking of nacre providing a micrometre-thick coating with a high platelet volume fraction, approaching that of natural nacre, with a high degree of platelet alignment. The toughening mechanisms of nacre, such as platelet sliding and interlocking as well as the ability to deflect a crack in a three-dimensional fashion, were found to occur also at the shortened length scale. This coating possessed an elastic modulus and hardness close to that of natural nacre. Low organic content along with a well-defined “brick-and-mortar” nanostructure are two criteria required to enable the reproduction of the mechanical properties and failure mechanisms of natural nacre. In addition, to achieve high stiffness and strength along with the reproduction of the classic deformation mechanism of natural nacre, our nanostructured artificial nacre allows for substantial plastic deformation upon loading as evidenced by a yielding of about 95%, significantly higher than natural nacre. We can conclude that a higher volume of platelet interface per unit volume may enable more platelet sliding/interlocking and, therefore, more energy dissipation. The well-arranged bio-inspired hybrid nanocomposites open-up the possibility to manufacture lightweight materials with excellent mechanical performance, such as the combination of high toughness, strength and stiffness along with unprecedented robustness.

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